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VI: Tocqueville and the Racial Contract

“White Supremacy is the unnamed political System that has made the modern world what it is today,” Charles Mills’ opening words to his famous *Racial Contract* are profound, declarative, enlightening, and in some sense, his battle cry. Mills argues in this important work that underlying any of the political systems in the modern day (and for the immediately foreseeable future) is the most prevalent and powerful political ideology that has remained unclassified as a political ideology by the mainstream intellectual powers and institutions. That ideology is the system of global white supremacy. As he points out, so much of western thought and political philosophy specifically has gone out of its way to exclude race in theory. At the same time, the “Racial Contract” as he puts it, is hidden between the lines or is taken as a premise. Mills’ particular philosophy in *Racial Contract* is a new framework that can allow us to take a very important look at what western thought (and its major players) have been saying behind the scenes, even if they might have been oblivious to its existence. A great example of these effects, it will be argued, are seen in Alexis de Tocqueville, an important political author of the 19th century, whose writings have many curious implications and contradictions that the

Racial Contract might be able to make sense of later, allowing us to answer the question: “Is Tocqueville part of the problem or the solution?”

To understand the question previously asked, we need to understand the framework we are using. Early on in his book, the *Racial Contract*, Mills says that the Racial contract has the “best claim to actually being an actual historical fact” and wholeheartedly believes this to be the case.¹²² “Race is socio-political rather than biological, but it is nonetheless real.”¹²³ This conflicts with the common notion that “race is not real, and therefore we should ignore it,” which several today hold. Many in today’s world argue “any law that is not colorblind is racist,” but Mills has challenged that idea, as he himself states that the “illusory color blindness actually entrenches white privilege.”¹²⁴ Race is real, but it is not biological. We must look at what it truly is and understand it from this different perspective if we are to really begin to combat racism and prejudice in this previously unnamed political system. As Mills says, “[white people are] permanently locked into a cognitive state of superstition and ignorance.”¹²⁵ This attitude has been an important factor in the continuation of racism in our modern day. Race isn't biological, it is a sociopolitical creation that has been used to discredit or oppress peoples for thousands of years, since the beginning of what could be considered society or politics. The Racial Contract affects everyone in different ways, some of which may remain unseen. These new principles in his framework are what make us ask new questions, making this theory a critical one.

Another important aspect of Mills’ Racial Contract is its relationship to other social contracts. Mills claims that the Racial Contract always comes before the “actual” social contract and modifies it; he says “The Racial Contract, therefore underwrites the social contract, is a

¹²² Charles W. Mills, *The Racial Contract*, (Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press, 1997), 20.

¹²³ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 126.

¹²⁴ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 77.

¹²⁵ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 44.

visible or hidden operator that restricts and modifies the scope of its prescriptions.”¹²⁶ The Racial Contract *always* comes before the social contract, rewriting it, because for there to be a social contract, there must have been a people, a polity. Additionally, there is a larger group of people, not all of whom make it into the polity. These individuals are not seen as whole people, but rather as subhumans, undeserving of the full range of human rights and dignities. Prior to the creation of a society, or the writing of a constitution, such as in American history, for example, the leaders of the polity gathered together to decide what political and social systems they would all agree on. Almost like an actual social contract being written, and like Mills says the Racial Contract precedes this one. There is a reason not a single black person in colonial America had their voice heard, and it’s not because they did not voice their concerns and beliefs. It’s because prior to the actual creation of the society and its rules (and even its groundwork), there was in place a Racial Contract that defined who was given full personhood. The issues with this are evident as they should have always been.

As mentioned before, an integral part of Mills’ work is its nature as a critique of the social contract tradition and its prominent thinkers for their hand in the continuance of the Racial Contract, due to their either their inherent racism found within their writings or their inaction against the already established framework of the Racial Contract. John Locke’s political writings are held up as the inspiration for the Constitution of the United States and his works are some of the most widely read in political theory courses in American colleges and universities. But how can we look at the political works of a man who was so influential in the operation of the Atlantic Slave Trade? Locke does not speak out in any capacity against slavery, but in fact, profited from it and excused its existence. Many more philosophers and political thinkers profited from slavery and the Racial Contract. Mills might argue that there would be only a

¹²⁶ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 72.

handful of exceptions: “All whites are beneficiaries to the Racial Contract, though some Whites are not *signatories* to it.”¹²⁷ Everyone who has “whiteness” benefits from the Racial Contract, even if they speak out against it, which few did. Other prominent thinkers such as Kant, Hobbes, and Thomas Jefferson professed their racism, based on the “scientific racism” of the time. Mills’ claims that these thinkers are racist based on their scientific racism, true hatred for another race, or that they are suffering from “an epistemology of ignorance,” a willful self-deception that makes them blind to the kind of prejudice that their policies and philosophies produce because it does not happen to people who have the same skin color. As Mills states in one of his main theses, “the Racial Contract tracks the actual moral/political consciousness of (most) white moral agents”¹²⁸ and “The Racial Contract is enforced through violence and ideological conditioning.”¹²⁹ This worldwide systematic racism outlined and described by the Racial Contract is so thorough and deeply ingrained in everyone that for some individuals it remains invisible and undetected. But its vestiges still affect their worldview.

One political philosopher, in particular, that would be interesting to examine with the Racial Contract in mind is Alexis de Tocqueville. A Frenchman who came to Jacksonian America in 1831 in an effort to learn about the state of the nation and how it functioned from an outside perspective, with his most known book being *Democracy in America*. He writes about the fundamental principles of American democracy, society, and culture regarding their difference from European nations like France, comparing and contrasting the two. He wrote about the separation of church and state, individual rights, and liberties. He saw America as (at the time) the best example of democracy.

¹²⁷ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 11.

¹²⁸ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 91.

¹²⁹ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 81.

I wish to set out the general tendencies of democratic societies of which no complete example yet exists—I confess that in America I saw more than America; I saw there the image of democracy itself with its inclinations, its character, its prejudices, and its passions, in order to learn what we have to fear or to hope from its progress.¹³⁰

Tocqueville was a proponent of democracy, even after witnessing the blatant issues with America at the time, mainly racism. Because he praised American society, it was thought that he *must* be a racist and supportive of slavery and racial injustice. In his article *Tocqueville as a Critical Race Theorist*, Alvin Tillery explored Tocqueville’s commonality with the critical race theorists of the modern day. “Tocqueville’s willingness to endorse the American Experiment even after witnessing the depths of racial inequality in the Jacksonian context has convinced most scholars that he failed to grasp the centrality of this fissure in American society and politics.”¹³¹

Especially with some of the language that he uses to describe black people, as pointed out in the article, “His Face,” Tocqueville writes of black physiognomy, “appears hideous to us, his intelligence limited, and his tastes low; we almost take him for some being between beast and man.”¹³² These writings show a clear racist belief against black people in America. But in the same article that Tillery wrote, he shows an example of Tocqueville disagreeing with some of his contemporaries on biological differences in race and agreeing with Charles Mills’ notion previously mentioned metaphysical theory of race as a concept. “[his] correspondence with Joseph Arthur de Gabineau...the ‘father of European Racism’...reveals his staunch opposition to naturalistic conceptions of racial difference.”¹³³

¹³⁰ David Riesman, “Tocqueville as Ethnographer,” *The American Scholar* 30, no. 2 (1961), 174–87, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/41208827>, 175.

¹³¹ Alvin B. Tillery, “Tocqueville as Critical Race Theorist: Whiteness as Property, Interest Convergence, and the Limits of Jacksonian Democracy,” *Political Research Quarterly* 62, no. 4 (2009), 639–52, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/25594436>, 639.

¹³² Tillery, “Tocqueville as Critical Race Theorist: Whiteness as Property, Interest Convergence, and the Limits of Jacksonian Democracy,” 641.

¹³³ Tillery, “Tocqueville as Critical Race Theorist: Whiteness as Property, Interest Convergence, and the Limits of Jacksonian Democracy,” 641.

However, things are not as simple as they might appear when dealing with Alexis de Tocqueville. Tillery argues that de Tocqueville might just be one of the first critical race theorists, a group who reject the notion that there are biological or scientific differences between the races, but rather, as Mills says, race is a socio-politically generated concept. While many people might believe that Tocqueville is a foil to critical race theorists, Tillery finds ample commonality between them.

Tocqueville's belief that social relation and the class are the sources of racial differences is the first place where there are similarities...[he] also shares the criticalists' position that white privilege is endemic in American culture and that both the laws and outcomes in democratic politics are functions of social reality...Moreover [he] joins the critical race theorists in positing that the American Race system generates negative externalities for whites.¹³⁴

From this, we can gather that Tocqueville agrees with Mills on many things, even if he was unaware of the full scope of the Racial Contract and how he was a part of it. Tillery also says that "Tocqueville's...beliefs that white privilege and racism are so entrenched in American 'mores' that genuine reform will be impossible without a complete dismantling of the system."¹³⁵ This certainly makes him sound somewhat like a critical race theorist. Additionally, Tocqueville's chapter on the "Three Races" tells us that he was one of the earliest white proponents of the social construction thesis, opposite the primordial notion that racism is created by biological or scientific differences between races. Tocqueville understands that racism is a prevalent and dangerous issue and that it is endemic to American Society, but he still praises the "American Experiment" after his visit and during the writing of *Democracy in America*. What are we to make of this?

¹³⁴ Tillery, "Tocqueville as Critical Race Theorist: Whiteness as Property, Interest Convergence, and the Limits of Jacksonian Democracy," 640.

¹³⁵ Tillery, "Tocqueville as Critical Race Theorist: Whiteness as Property, Interest Convergence, and the Limits of Jacksonian Democracy," 640.

Charles Mills might say that Alexis de Tocqueville is suffering from the Racial Contract in a different way than non-white people suffer from it. It has possibly been so ingrained into him, that it, as Mills put it, “is like the water to a fish, or air to man,” the surroundings, invisible to those that have grown accustomed to it or have lived their whole lives knowing nothing else but the Racial Contract, as the most basic of political axioms. In another of Charles Mills’ famous works, *Black Rights/White Wrongs*, he calls Toqueville out by name,

Taking the writings of Alexis de Tocqueville....as exemplary...shows that even when they admit the existence of racism and sexism in national practices, public policy, legal rules, and central ideologies. They still fall back on the conceptualization of an essentially inclusive “liberal democracy.” So racism and sexism are framed as “anomalies” to a political culture conceived of as-despite everything—basically egalitarian.¹³⁶

This is a perfect example of the social and ideological conditioning that takes place during the Racial Contract to ensure that even “intellectuals” adhere to it with seemingly inherent contradictions within their writings or their conclusions. The problem is so widespread that Mills makes this same claim of many of the most prominent philosophers and intellectuals in the mainstream canon, listing explicitly: Plato, Aristotle, Aquinas, Hobbes, Hume, Locke, Rousseau, Kant, Hegel, and more.¹³⁷ Even when the ideal theorists can point out the systemic flaws in democracy or systems of politics, they, in the end, decide that racism is not a deciding factor in what makes a political or ideological system just, or at least it can be overlooked as not a serious enough problem.

Alexis de Tocqueville is, without a doubt, a proponent of democracy, especially at the time of his writing *Democracy in America*. However, this political system has very serious issues according to Charles Mills and his framework of the *Racial Contract*. One of the most interesting

¹³⁶ Charles W. Mills, *Black Rights/White Wrongs: The Critique of Racial Liberalism*, (New York, NY: Oxford University Press, 2017), 89.

¹³⁷ Mills, *Black Rights/White Wrongs: The Critique of Racial Liberalism*, 86.

principles in liberalism and social contracts to examine in this framework is the concept of tyranny of the majority and the rights of the minority. Many people understand America to be a democracy, but this is not true, the United States is a constitutional republic. Unlike Democracy, which will prioritize the needs of the many over the needs of the few, a constitutional republic will outline in its constitution the rights and liberties of all individuals within the society, and these rights cannot be violated in favor of the needs of the many. But Tocqueville saw a sense in which there is democracy in America, because it looked much more like democracy than his

native France at the time. The Constitution itself makes claims about the freedoms of American citizens that have not been fulfilled. As Martin Luther King Jr. said in the famous “I Have a

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Dream” speech, “America has given the Negro People a check, a check which has come back marked ‘insufficient funds.’” The American government since the Declaration of Independence has claimed that “all men are created equal,” but looking through our nation’s history, we can see that we have not always lived up to that ideal either. No political system of government is perfect, but that is not an excuse for injustice. A million American citizens cannot justify killing a lottery winner and distributing their winnings to a larger population because the individual rights of the lottery winner protect them from the tyranny of the majority. And 51% of the country does not and cannot have the right to enslave 49% of the country. America has always (since its creation as a European colony-turned-nation-state), been a nation where a majority of the population has been White. Further, it has always been a nation where Whites have had a monopoly on wealth, social status, and political power. The path of these facts to the notion of the tyranny of the majority is obvious.

While Tocqueville praised the democratic system in America, he still criticized the potential for it to develop into a tyranny of the majority which would encroach upon the civil liberties of the individual. In Morton Horwitz's article *Tocqueville and the Tyranny of the Majority*, he gives clearer insight into Tocqueville's mindset: "Tocqueville describes America but thinks of Europe."¹³⁸ Tocqueville was looking at the democratic system and society in America and comparing it to France, which was "already on the road to its second Napoleonic Despotism." While America was certainly not perfect, Tocqueville was looking to us as a higher standard and an example by which France could redirect itself to a better course. In his own opinion, Tocqueville did not believe that there was a deep and permanent division in the two communities of America, those being the majority and minority groups. He claimed that in American society, it was rare for laws to be arbitrary or unjustly coercive when created solely by the majority. Instead of the tyranny of the majority being found in the law books, Tocqueville said that it can be found in social dynamics and unwritten rules and mores of the community. As Tocqueville himself stated, these social dynamics and cultural norms can be changed over time by black people themselves: "If ever America undergoes great revolutions, they will be brought about by the presence of the black race on the soil of the United States - that is to say, they will owe their origin, not to the equality but the inequality of conditions." This does not sound like a racist philosopher from the 19th century but sounds like something that was pulled from the mind of a young Charles Mills. Tocqueville is saying that a revolution in America would owe itself to black people, the minority versus the majority. At the time of his visit and his writing, race relations in American society would seem inexcusable to us today, but for Tocqueville, perhaps the Racial Contract blinded him to how much of an injustice this was. On the other hand,

¹³⁸ Morton J. Horwitz, "Tocqueville and the Tyranny of the Majority," *The Review of Politics* 28, no. 3 (1966), 293-307, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1405588>, 295

perhaps the Racial Contract had successfully maintained its hold on him to where he was unable to resolve the contradictions in his logic, much like the discussion between differing views of Kant, *was he a consistent inegalitarian or an inconsistent egalitarian?* These are the questions hidden by the Racial Contract, and through these questions, we can see once again how white supremacy and the Racial Contract was a part of Tocqueville's thoughts.

Going back to questions posed earlier in this paper, what is Alexis de Tocqueville? Is he a racist, or a critical race theorist? Is he part of the problem of racial injustice, or was he ahead of his time? It can be argued that Tocqueville truly believed in a more modern critical race theory but was a victim of the Racial Contract's epistemology of ignorance and of being a product of his time, where such racism was more commonplace and unspoken.

Tocqueville's praises of Jacksonian America make him seem as though he is part of the problem, akin to someone such as Locke. His failures to overcome the Racial Contract also, as this paper has shown, are a great example of many of the principles of Mills' Racial Contract. His beliefs on the tyranny of the majority are that the mechanism of this kind of tyranny was not the law but in the mores of the culture, which can be changed by a revolution. Also, any revolution in America would owe itself to black people and the inequality of conditions. As Tillery puts it, "Tocqueville states explicitly that blacks have the potential to "change" their condition and "induce the whites to abandon the opinion they have conceived of the intellectual and moral inferiority of the race."¹³⁹ These things combined seem to make him part of the solution more so than the problem. But overall, it seems like he is both part of the problem and a part of the solution. This is based on his refusals; to refuse naturalistic and scientific racism and

¹³⁹ Tillery, "Tocqueville as Critical Race Theorist: Whiteness as Property, Interest Convergence, and the Limits of Jacksonian Democracy," 643.

his refusal to condemn America for its racial injustice together are the contradicting and complicated evidence to these questions.

Charles Mills' revolutionary works such as *The Racial Contract* and *Black Rights/White Wrongs* are radical critiques of the global tradition of western philosophy, a declaration and condemnation of its proliferation of global white superiority as a political system prior to all others. This new framework makes us ask many new questions about the validity of old ideas and the history of philosophy in general. Alexis de Tocqueville, a French writer who supported the American experiment of democracy, obviously saw the racism in Jacksonian America in the 1830s but still praised the nation. While there are many similarities in his writings to current-day critical race theorists, they would *never* praise a society with such rampant racism, sexism, and even more issues. Tocqueville is a beneficiary (and also possibly suffers from the social conditioning and epistemology of ignorance) of the Racial Contract. And because of this, Tocqueville was both part of the problem and the solution to racism in America. In closing, Mills' new framework to view the western political world is a fine macro and microscope that allows us to look at everything in a new, more conscious, and enlightening way, to hopefully understand the world of today and how it has been shaped by the Racial Contract. While we can admit his faults, we can agree to learn from Tocqueville, and be a part of what he called America's strength, our ability to repair our faults. We can be the change we want there to be in America by not rejecting a whole point of view because of flaws, but by still embracing its strongest points and sticking to our convictions.